

ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Training Analytics

Interest in Training Activities

Preferred Format

Learning Platform Familiarity

Working Language

Training Analytics

Functional Role	What is your highest level of education completed?					Totale generale
	BA / BSc (Bachelor's degree)	High school diploma or equivalent	I prefer not to answer	MA / MSc (Master's degree)	PhD or equivalent (Doctoral level)	
Administration and Management (e.g. Director, Project Manager, etc.)	12,28%	5,26%	1,75%	36,84%	43,86%	100,00%
Architect / Built heritage specialist	5,26%	5,26%		47,37%	42,11%	100,00%
Conservator/Restorer	17,24%	3,45%		48,28%	31,03%	100,00%
Curator, archivist	16,67%			50,00%	33,33%	100,00%
Database and digital collection managers	7,14%	3,57%		32,14%	57,14%	100,00%
Digitization experts (3D scanning, digital archiving)	6,12%	8,16%	4,08%	44,90%	36,73%	100,00%
Heritage scientist	8,70%	8,70%		13,04%	69,57%	100,00%
Historians and archaeologists	6,35%		1,59%	30,16%	61,90%	100,00%
Museum educators / Heritage interpreters				46,67%	53,33%	100,00%
VR-AR specialist	7,14%			50,00%	42,86%	100,00%
Totale generale	8,01%	3,86%	1,19%	38,58%	48,37%	100,00%

Plan to Apply Acquired Skills

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Functional Role	Topics Familiarity										
	AVERAGE di Digital Twins potentialities and advantages (e.g., real-time data, decision support)	AVERAGE di 2D/3D digitisation (e.g. scanning, photogrammetry, GIS)	AVERAGE di Creating or editing 3D models (e.g. mesh editing, modelling software)	AVERAGE di Using or navigating 3D simulations (e.g., virtual walkthroughs, scenario exploration)	AVERAGE di Analysing data from 3D simulations (e.g., condition monitoring, material behaviour analysis)	AVERAGE di Using AR/VR tools in cultural heritage (e.g., virtual exhibitions, AR applications)	AVERAGE di IoT / IoCT services (e.g., sensor networks, remote monitoring)	AVERAGE di Working with digital environments / virtual machines (e.g. cloud platforms, emulated lab setups)	AVERAGE di Metadata standards (e.g. Dublin Core, LIDO)	AVERAGE di Semantic data modelling (e.g. CIDOC CRM, ontologies)	AVERAGE di Managing or aggregating data from different sources (e.g., database integration, harvesting protocols)
Administration and Management	2,01	2,80	2,12	2,45	1,91	2,12	1,62	2,31	2,19	2,05	2,22
Architect / Built heritage specialist	2,51	3,29	3,16	2,97	2,61	2,13	1,89	2,03	1,47	1,61	1,92
Conservator/Restorer	1,45	2,34	1,86	1,93	1,76	1,50	1,66	1,79	1,59	1,62	1,83
Curator, archivist	1,17	2,17	1,33	1,67	1,00	1,67	1,50	1,33	1,33	1,00	1,33
Database and digital collection managers	2,50	3,25	2,25	2,25	1,79	2,00	2,02	3,21	3,21	3,46	3,64
Digitization experts (3D scanning, digital)	2,89	4,32	3,92	3,26	2,48	2,69	1,76	2,37	2,29	2,22	2,26
Heritage scientist	2,57	2,96	2,65	2,17	2,09	1,91	2,30	2,65	1,96	2,00	2,39
Historians and archaeologists	1,89	2,77	2,34	2,43	1,83	2,00	1,43	2,22	2,19	2,14	2,09
Museum educators / Heritage	2,63	2,78	2,22	2,60	2,12	2,57	1,80	2,40	1,93	1,87	2,10
VR-AR specialist	3,21	3,64	3,71	3,93	2,36	4,07	2,00	2,57	2,00	1,93	2,36
Totale generale	2,29	3,10	2,63	2,60	2,07	2,22	1,75	2,32	2,09	2,08	2,24

Functional Role & Interest in Learning more (Topic-based visualization)

Familiarity with Topics & Interest in learning more

Functional Role & Interest in Learning more (Role-based comparison)

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What is your main working language?																			
Country	Czech	Dutch	English	French	German	Greek	Italian	Lithuanian	Norwegian	Polish	Portuguese	Romanian	Serbian	Slovene	Spanish	Turkish	Ukrainian	Totale generale	
Austria	0		4		7													11	
Belgium	0	6	6	4														16	
Brazil											1							1	
Bulgaria			2															2	
Canada			2															2	
Croatia			3															3	
Cyprus			1															1	
Czech Republic (Czechia)	2																	2	
Denmark			1															1	
Finland	0		1															1	
France			2	1														3	
Germany	0		7		15													22	
Greece	0		12	2		25												39	
India			2															2	
Indonesia			1															1	
Ireland			1															1	
Italy	0		24				95											119	
Japan			1															1	
Lithuania			1					1										2	
Netherlands	0	4	2															6	
North Macedonia						1												1	
Norway									2									2	
Poland			1							1								2	
Portugal			3								2							5	
Romania												2						2	
Serbia			2										1					3	
Slovenia	0		2											17				19	
Spain	0		1												5			6	
Switzerland			3		3													6	
Turkey			1													1		2	
Ukraine			2														2	4	
United Kingdom			8															8	
United States of America			2															2	
Totale generale	0	2	10	98	7	25	26	95	1	2	1	3	2	1	17	5	1	2	298